

EFFECTS INFLUENCING THE FIBRE CONCENTRATION DEPENDENCE OF TENSILE STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL, SHORT-GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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In injection moulded samples of grp the fibres are highly oriented in flow direction. In this direction failure strength increases initially almost linear with fibre volume fraction. This behaviour is well described by Kelly's model. At higher fibre concentrations, the increment of failure strength is substantially reduced, which is ascribed to i) decreasing fibre length due to increasing fibre attrition during processing, ii) misalignment of fibres, iii) premature delamination of fibres during deformation, iiiii) change of fracture mode.

I. INTRODUCTION

The tensile strength of short glass fibre-reinforced plastics (grp) depends on many parameters which are either inherent to the product (i.e. fibre concentration, interfacial shear strength) or dependent on the processing methods (i.e. fibre length, fibre orientation). This paper deals with effects which influence the dependence of the tensile strength of injection moulded samples on the fibre concentration. As an example, the standardized dumb-bell test piece (ISO-R 527, Type 1 test specimen; DIN 53 455, Stab 3) was studied. This type of specimen is of fundamental importance in material science, because the characterization of many mechanical properties of materials rests upon it.

II. DEFORMATION BEHAVIOUR OF GRP

As is well known from the literature and displayed in Fig. 1 for glass fibre-reinforced polyamide 6, the tensile strength of

Fig. 1: Failure strength of gfr pa

injection moulded dumb-bell test pieces increases almost linearly with the fibre volume fraction up to about 15 %, and if the matrix is not too brittle [1]. Such linear relationships are always advantageous for manufacturing as well as for design purposes. The linear increase of failure strength with concentration is consistent with Kelly's model [2] which assumes the fibres to be stressed along their

$$\hat{\sigma}_{fm} = \left(\frac{\tau_{fm}}{2 r_f} \bar{l} - \sigma'_m \right) v_f + \sigma'_m \quad (1)$$

$\hat{\sigma}_{fm}$ = failure strength of the composite

τ_{fm} = interfacial shear strength

r_f = fibre radius

\bar{l} = mean fibre length

σ'_m = stress in the matrix at the onset of failure or failure of matrix

v_f = volume fraction of fibres

axis by shear stresses acting at the fibre surface. The interfacial shear strength which means the maximum stress sustainable by the interface without delamination of the fibre has been assessed from the initial slope of the tensile strength-concentration-curve according to the rearranged Eq. (1)

$$\tau_{fm} = \frac{2 r_f}{l} \left(\frac{d \hat{\sigma}_{fm}}{d v_f} + \sigma'_m \right) \quad (2)$$

Data are given in Ref. [1] for various materials with different coupling agents on the fibres. At higher fibre concentrations, substantial deviation from this linearity is observed in the direction of lower failure strengths. As an example, Fig. 2 shows the situation for glass fibre-reinforced polyamide, measured at room temperature

Fig. 2: Failure strength of fibre-reinforced pa

with a strain rate of about 0.2 min^{-1} . The products and the specimens were manufactured under comparable conditions, but at different times, to demonstrate reproducibility (series 1 and 2). The fibres have a diameter of $10 \mu\text{m}$ and were treated with a sizing and coupling agent causing good adhesion between the fibres and the matrix. The interfacial shear strength evaluated for the product of Fig. 2 is $\tau_{fm} = 39 \text{ N/mm}^2$ which equals within the limits of resolution and test scatter the matrix shear strength

$$\tau_{f1} = \frac{\sigma_y}{\sqrt{3}} = 44 \text{ N/mm}^2 \quad (\sigma_y = \text{yield stress of the matrix}).$$

The latter value is based on the v. Mises criterion [3]. To understand the reduced reinforcement of fibres at higher concentrations, four premises leading to linearity according to Kelly's model were regarded in more detail and were found to be not valid in injection moulded pieces. These four detrimental effects on the failure strength with rising fibre concentration are

1. decreasing fibre length due to increasing fibre attrition during processing,
2. misalignment of fibres,
3. premature delamination of fibres during deformation,
4. change of fracture mode.

The contributions of the first three effects are quantified in Fig. 2.

III. EFFECTS REDUCING TENSILE STRENGTH OF GRP.

III.1 FIBRE SHORTENING

In processed fibre-reinforced thermoplastics the lengths of glass fibres are not uniform. The length distribution of the fibres was in our case determined by counting 500 single fibres under the microscope; these were collected from a sample after the matrix had been burnt off. From this frequency distribution functions for which examples are given in Ref. [1] one can define either the number average length $\Sigma z_i l_i$ [1] or the median length l_{50} which is the characteristic length at 50 per cent fibre population. In Fig. 3 the l_{50} -values are plotted as a function of the fibre volume fraction

Fig. 3: Length of fibres at 50 % number fraction

for both series. Two experimental points for the same material represent two measurements and reveal the reproducibility of the determination method. The lengths of the fibres decrease with increasing fibre concentration due to the enhanced fibre attrition during compounding the product. Considering this concentration dependence of the fibre length in Eq. (1), with $\bar{l} = l_{50}$, one obtains the failure strength as a function of the fibre concentration. This relationship is shown in Fig. 2 and explains the reduced reinforcement to a great deal (fibre shortening).

III.2 MISALIGNMENT OF FIBRES

The orientation of the fibres can be measured by the technique of x-ray projection microscopy in the SEM [4]. Fig. 4 shows as an example for this technique the x-ray projection of a sheet parallel to the cross sections, and two further sheets, one containing the small the other containing the broad side of the specimen. The sheets were microtomed from a specimen containing 10 % fibres. Most of the fibres are aligned in the flow and tensile direction. But in the center of the specimens fibres are oriented oblique to the flow direction. Because it seemed to us too elaborate to measure the orientation distribution function for all specimens, we determined the volume in which the fibres are inclined more than 30° to the tensile direction. These fibres were assumed not to contribute to the tensile strength, whereas all other fibres are regarded to be completely aligned in tensile direction. The inclination angle of

Fig. 4: Fibre orientation in injection moulded gr. (10 %) pa

30° was chosen as a limiting value because, as shown in a former paper [1], products with fibres preferentially orientated 30° inclined to the tensile direction yielded a tensile increments due to fibres which was about half the value of the tensile increment in specimens with fibre orientation in tensile direction. The volume fraction of fibres misaligned more than 30° is shown in Fig. 5. The volume fraction of misaligned fibres increases with concentration. The

Fig. 5: Volume fraction of fibres declined more than 30° to the tensile direction

stress reduction caused by these misaligned and presumable not active fibres was calculated by

$$\Delta \hat{\sigma}_{fm} = \left(\frac{\tau_{fm}}{2 r_f} l_{50} - \sigma'_m \right) \Delta v_f \quad (3)$$

In Fig. 2, these stress reductions were subtracted from the curve which accounts for the fibre length shortening, leading to the curve for misalignment.

III.3 PREMATURE DELAMINATION OF FIBRES

Eq. (1) which describes the dependence of tensile strength on fibre concentration is based upon the assumption that all fibres are stress bearing up to the failure strength of the composite. There are indications that the failure of short fibres in plastics is mainly given by delamination and to a far less extent, if at all, by fibre fracture [1]. One can conjecture that due to the different strains in the matrix and fibre material during deformation some fibres delaminate from the matrix already before failure of the composite, especially, if the bonding is not high enough or sizing defects are present. Thereby voids are formed at least at the ends of the fibres.

To get some indication where this delamination process starts during deformation, we measured the volume change during deformation in a dilatometer, where the deforming specimen is immersed in water. When delamination occurs the concomitant voiding at the end of the fibres and microcracks should increase the volume of the product. Fig. 7 shows some experimental results. The pure matrix material deforms after the initial elastic region beyond the yield point only by shearing, without cavitation processes. On the other hand in

Fig. 7: Change of volume during deformation

the highly reinforced material the volume does not increase steadily before failure. In less reinforced products volume change does not differ significantly in respect to the pure matrix material.

To assess quantitatively the drop in failure strength due to the premature delamination of fibres we measured the Young's modulus E_{fm} of the specimen in its virgin state and 24 hours after deformation up to a level shortly before fracture. The drop of modulus ΔE was associated with premature delamination of fibres, their volume fraction Δv_f^E was assessed according to the relation

$$\Delta v_f^E = \frac{\Delta E_{fm}}{d E_{fm} / d v_f} \quad (4)$$

The increase of Young's modulus with volume fibre fraction $d E_{fm} / d v_f$ has been formerly [5] determined to be 42 000 [N/mm² volume fraction]. The values for Δv_f^E are shown in Fig. 8 (decay of Young's modulus).

Fig. 8: Volume fraction of ineffective fibres after predeformation

The results are comparable within the limits with those we got by measuring the failure stress decay after predeformation (residual strength decay). The average values (solid line in Fig. 8) of the delaminated fibre concentrations are used to recalculate by Eq. (3) the stress weakening which is taken into consideration in Fig. 2.

III.4 FAILURE MODE

Involving enhanced fibre attrition, misalignment of fibres, and premature delamination of fibres (hatched area in Fig. 2), Kelly's model describes the tensile strength of glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics satisfactorily, except at the very high volume fraction of fibres above 0.5 which corresponds to about 67 wt % fibres. Beyond this concentration the failure strength decays drastically. The reason for this further deterioration of failure strength is indicated by looking at the fracture surface. Kelly's model is based on the assumption that cracks propagate perpendicular to the fibres pulling them out of the matrix. This assumption seems to be valid at lower fibre concentrations (see Fig. 9, left hand side). But at the highest concentration cracks run locally along fibres which are inclined to the tensile direction (Fig. 9, right hand side). So,

Fig. 9 : X-ray projection micrographs of fractured gfr. pa
(side view)

fracture changes from normal to shear mode. Shear fracture is, however, not included in Kelly's model. Presently, we are not able to quantify failure strength when the material fails partly in shear mode. But it can easily be realized that failure stress is decreased if the fibres are not pulled out of the matrix and crack does not cross the fibres. First indications of this shear effect can already be discerned at a somewhat lower fibre concentration (Fig. 10) where sheets cut perpendicular through the two fracture surfaces reveal the partly conical shape of the fracture surface as predestinated by the pattern of fibre orientation. Additionally, at high fibre concentration the single fibres can no longer be regarded as individuals, but rather as clusters with presumable reduced effectiveness (Fig. 11).

Fig. 10: Fracture of glass-fibre-reinforced (67 %) pa

Fig. 11: SEM of fracture surfaces of glass-fibre-reinforced pa

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